

Detecting Bookmaker Odds Mistakes Using Linear Algebra and Statistical Methods

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Abstract

Bookmakers occasionally set incorrect odds, leading to arbitrage opportunities or potential financial loss. This paper presents a mathematical framework using linear algebra, partial differential equations, and statistical methods to detect outliers in bookmakers' odds across multiple dimensions. We derive new formulas utilizing machine learning techniques and partial differentials to analyze and adjust bets. An example is provided to illustrate the detection of an outlier bookmaker. It is also noted that bookmakers reserve the right to revert bets in case of mistakes, as per their terms and conditions.

Introduction

Bookmakers offer odds on various outcomes of sporting events, reflecting their assessment of the probability of each outcome. These odds are crucial for bettors making informed decisions. However, mistakes in setting odds can occur due to human error, miscalculations, or outdated information. Identifying these mistakes is valuable for both bettors and bookmakers. Bettors can exploit mispriced odds for profit, while bookmakers can adjust their odds to minimize risk.

This paper enhances the mathematical modeling of bookmakers' odds using linear algebra and partial differential equations. By representing odds in a high-dimensional space and employing differential calculus, we develop tools to detect anomalies and optimize betting strategies.

Mathematical Modeling of Odds in n Dimensions

Representation of Odds as Vectors

Consider an event with n possible outcomes. Each bookmaker i provides a vector of odds:

$$\mathbf{o}_i = [o_{i1}, o_{i2}, \dots, o_{in}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

The corresponding implied probabilities are:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = [p_{i1}, p_{i2}, \dots, p_{in}]^T = \left[\frac{1}{o_{i1}}, \frac{1}{o_{i2}}, \dots, \frac{1}{o_{in}} \right]^T$$

Since bookmakers include a margin (overround), we normalize these probabilities:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{p}_i}{\mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{p}_i}$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the vector of ones.

Odds Space and Simplex

The normalized implied probabilities $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i$ lie within the $(n-1)$ -dimensional simplex Δ^{n-1} , defined as:

$$\Delta^{n-1} = \left\{ \mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \sum_{j=1}^n p_j = 1, p_j \geq 0 \forall j \right\}$$

This representation allows us to analyze the bookmakers' implied probability distributions using linear algebra tools.

Covariance Matrix of Odds

We can construct a covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}$ of the normalized probabilities across all bookmakers:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})(\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})^\top$$

where m is the number of bookmakers and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the mean probability vector:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i$$

The covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}$ captures the variability and correlations between the probabilities assigned to different outcomes.

Detecting Outliers Using Linear Algebra

Mahalanobis Distance

To identify outliers, we can use the Mahalanobis distance, which accounts for the covariance structure of the data:

$$D_i = \sqrt{(\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1} (\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})}$$

A high Mahalanobis distance indicates that bookmaker i 's odds are an outlier compared to other bookmakers.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

By performing PCA on the covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}$, we can reduce the dimensionality and identify directions (principal components) with the most variance. The eigenvectors $\mathbf{v}_k$ and eigenvalues λ_k satisfy:

$$\mathbf{C}\mathbf{v}_k = \lambda_k \mathbf{v}_k$$

We can project the normalized probabilities onto the principal components:

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{V}^\top (\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})$$

where $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n]$.

By analyzing the projections $\mathbf{z}_i$, we can detect bookmakers whose odds significantly deviate along principal components with high variance.

Deriving New Formulas with Partial Differentials and Machine Learning

Odds Adjustment via Gradient Descent

Assume we have a machine learning model predicting the "true" probabilities $\hat{\mathbf{p}} = [\hat{p}_1, \hat{p}_2, \dots, \hat{p}_n]^\top$ based on historical data and features $\mathbf{x}$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = f(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are the model parameters.

The loss function to minimize the discrepancy between bookmakers' normalized probabilities and the model's predictions is:

$$L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{i=1}^m |\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{p}}|^2$$

We can perform gradient descent to optimize $\boldsymbol{\theta}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{new}} = \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{old}} - \eta \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} L(\boldsymbol{\theta})$$

where η is the learning rate, and the gradient is:

$$\nabla_{\theta} L(\theta) = 2 \sum_{i=1}^m (\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{p}})^\top \left(-\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{p}}}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

Partial Differentials in Odds Optimization

Suppose we model the probabilities using a softmax function to ensure they sum to 1:

$$\hat{p}_j = \frac{e^{\Phi_j(\mathbf{x}, \theta)}}{\sum_{k=1}^n e^{\Phi_k(\mathbf{x}, \theta)}}$$

where $\Phi_j(\mathbf{x}, \theta)$ is a scoring function for outcome j .

The partial derivatives of the loss function with respect to θ are:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_l} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (\tilde{p}_{ij} - \hat{p}_j) \left(\hat{p}_j (\delta_{jl} - \hat{p}_l) \frac{\partial \Phi_j}{\partial \theta_l} \right)$$

where δ_{jl} is the Kronecker delta.

This gradient incorporates partial differentials of the scoring functions with respect to the parameters, allowing for precise adjustments in the model.

Example

Consider two bookmakers providing odds for a football match with three possible outcomes: Win (W), Draw (D), and Lose (L).

- **Bookmaker 1** odds: $\mathbf{o}_1 = [0.9, 25, 0.1]^\top$
- **Bookmaker 2** odds: $\mathbf{o}_2 = [1.2, 25, 25]^\top$

Calculating Implied Probabilities

For each bookmaker, we compute the implied probabilities and normalize them.

Bookmaker 1

Implied probabilities:

$$\mathbf{p}_1 = \left[\frac{1}{0.9}, \frac{1}{25}, \frac{1}{0.1} \right]^\top \approx [1.1111, 0.04, 10]^\top$$

Normalization constant:

$$S_1 = \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{p}_1 = 1.1111 + 0.04 + 10 = 11.1511$$

Normalized probabilities:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{p}_1}{S_1} \approx [0.0996, 0.0036, 0.8968]^\top$$

Bookmaker 2

Implied probabilities:

$$\mathbf{p}_2 = \left[\frac{1}{1.2}, \frac{1}{25}, \frac{1}{25} \right]^\top \approx [0.8333, 0.04, 0.04]^\top$$

Normalization constant:

$$S_2 = \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{p}_2 = 0.8333 + 0.04 + 0.04 = 0.9133$$

Normalized probabilities:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_2 = \frac{\mathbf{p}_2}{S_2} \approx [0.9124, 0.0438, 0.0438]^\top$$

Covariance Matrix and Mahalanobis Distance

Mean probability vector:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_1 + \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_2}{2} \approx [0.5060, 0.0237, 0.4703]^\top$$

Deviations from the mean:

$$\mathbf{d}_1 = \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_1 - \boldsymbol{\mu}, \quad \mathbf{d}_2 = \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_2 - \boldsymbol{\mu}$$

Covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{d}_1 \mathbf{d}_1^\top + \mathbf{d}_2 \mathbf{d}_2^\top)$$

Computing $\mathbf{C}$ and its inverse $\mathbf{C}^{-1}$:

$$\mathbf{C} \approx \begin{bmatrix} 0.3313 & 0.0214 & -0.3527 \\ 0.0214 & 0.0008 & -0.0222 \\ -0.3527 & -0.0222 & 0.3749 \end{bmatrix}$$

Assuming $\mathbf{C}$ is invertible, we compute Mahalanobis distances:

$$D_1 = \sqrt{\mathbf{d}_1^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1}, \quad D_2 = \sqrt{\mathbf{d}_2^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1} \mathbf{d}_2}$$

If D_i exceeds a critical value (e.g., corresponding to a high percentile of the chi-squared distribution with n degrees of freedom), bookmaker i is considered an outlier.

Principal Component Analysis

Eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $\mathbf{C}$:

$$\mathbf{C} \mathbf{v}_k = \lambda_k \mathbf{v}_k$$

Suppose we find significant variance along the first principal component. Projecting the deviations onto the principal components:

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{V}^\top \mathbf{d}_i$$

Analyzing $\mathbf{z}_i$, we may find that one bookmaker significantly deviates along a principal component, indicating an outlier.

Application of Partial Differential Equations

Modeling Odds Dynamics

Suppose we model the evolution of odds over time t using a partial differential equation (PDE):

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_{ij}}{\partial t} + \sum_{k=1}^n a_{jk} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_{ik}}{\partial x_k} = 0$$

where $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]^\top$ represents influencing factors (e.g., team statistics), and a_{jk} are coefficients capturing the relationship between factors and probabilities.

By solving this PDE, we can predict how odds should adjust given changes in influencing factors. Deviations from the predicted odds highlight potential mistakes.

Optimization Using the Euler-Lagrange Equation

We can frame the odds adjustment as an optimization problem:

$$\min_{\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i} \int L(\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i, \nabla \tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i, \mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}$$

subject to constraints (e.g., probabilities sum to 1).

Applying the calculus of variations, the Euler-Lagrange equation provides necessary conditions for optimality:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \tilde{p}_{ij}} - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{p}_{ij}}{\partial x_k} \right)} \right) = 0$$

Solving this equation yields the optimal probability distribution $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i$.

Bookmakers' Right to Revert Bets

Bookmakers often include terms and conditions stating that they reserve the right to void or adjust bets if an obvious error is detected in the odds. This is to protect themselves from significant losses due to mistakes. Bettors should be aware that even if they identify mispriced odds, the bookmaker may cancel the bet upon realizing the error.

Conclusion

By representing bookmakers' odds in an n -dimensional vector space and applying linear algebra and partial differential equations, we can detect potential mistakes in the odds. The use of covariance matrices, Mahalanobis distances, and PCA allows for a robust statistical analysis of bookmakers' odds. Machine learning models, optimized using gradient descent and partial differentials, further enhance this process by predicting expected probabilities and highlighting significant deviations. While this approach is valuable for identifying arbitrage opportunities, bettors must consider the bookmakers' rights to revert erroneous bets.

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